

COMPLEX SALTS OF BENZAMIDOXIME WITH METALS

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Complex compounds of copper, palladium, cobalt and nickel with benzamidoxime have been described and their magnetic properties studied. Nickel forms an insoluble red compound which is converted by alkalis into a highly soluble deep blue salt.

It has been shown that the red nickel complex does not contain any trivalent nickel atom, as represented by Dubský and co-workers but is, as usual, a derivative of bivalent nickel.

The action of iron^{III} chloride on benzamidoxime has also been studied.

Krüg (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 128, 1635; 1895, 18, 1054) observed that benzamidoxime gave an intense red coloration with ferric chloride. Werner (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1069) found that benzamidoxime gave a brown-green precipitate with a solution of copper^{II} salt. Dubský and co-workers (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Com.*, 1935, 7, 1) described the preparation of a red nickel salt of benzamidoxime which was regarded by them as a salt of trivalent nickel on account of its liberating iodine from acidified potassium iodide solution. Based on analytical data it was assigned the composition Ni [ON: (H₂N)C₆H₅]₃. They also obtained a green copper salt of composition C₆H₅.C(NH₂):NO.Cu(OH),H₂O. The present paper deals with the preparation, properties and magnetic behaviour of copper, palladium, cobalt and two nickel salts. The action of iron^{III} chloride solution on benzamidoxime has also been studied.

The green coloured copper salt is quantitatively precipitated from a solution of copper chloride or copper sulphate by benzamidoxime at a *p_H* of about 6.5–6.7 in presence of sodium acetate. The substance has been found to be paramagnetic ($\mu_s = 1.23$). The unusually low value of the magnetic moment indicates that the substance is probably a mixture of Cu^{II} and Cu^I salts of composition C₆H₅.C(NH₂):NO.Cu(OH) and C₆H₅.C(NH₂):NO.Cu, H₂O respectively, due to partial reduction of cupric copper by the reagent (cf. Krüg, *loc. cit.*).

The palladium salt was obtained as a yellowish orange precipitate from a solution of palladium^{II} chloride in aqueous sodium chloride by the addition of the requisite quantity of the amidoxime solution. The substance is diamagnetic as is to be expected for a square planar palladium^{II} complex.

The cobalt compound was prepared from dichloro-tetrapyridine-cobaltic chloride and benzamidoxime in presence of a small amount of sodium hydroxide. The substance on drying forms a brownish black powder which is paramagnetic. This is rather unusual for a cobaltic compound since only a few cobaltic compounds, e.g., the oxide and the fluoride, are paramagnetic.

On treating an ammoniacal solution of nickel chloride with benzamidoxime the blue colour of the solution was gradually intensified and on being allowed to stand in contact with air for a day or two the mixture slowly deposited needle-shaped red crystals. These were found to liberate iodine from an acidified KI solution. When an aqueous suspension of the red salt was treated with dimethylglyoxime and a little ammonia, all the nickel was precipitated, and the clear filtrate retained the oxidising action of the original compound. This clearly shows that the red nickel complex contains bivalent nickel and that its oxidising action is attributable to the character of the ligand. Since benzamidoxime alone or in the presence of nickel salt in acid solution does not liberate

the oxidation of the amidoxime is effected by air prior to the formation of the red nickel complex.

It was not possible to titrate the iodine liberated from potassium iodide by the red nickel salt as the end-point was rather fleeting and indefinite.

The red compound was found to lose ammonia on being treated with dilute alkali in the cold. It suffered no loss when dried over sulphuric acid *in vacuo*, indicating that the ammonia molecules are more or less firmly held inside the co-ordination zone.

Both red and blue nickel salts were found to be diamagnetic, as might be expected for square planar nickel^{II} complexes. It further disproves Dubský's supposition that the red salt contains tripositive nickel atom.

When a solution of ferric chloride was added to that of an excess of benzamidoxime, there appeared a brown coloured precipitate, which dissolved in excess of ferric chloride to form a dark red solution. With sodium hydroxide or ammonia this red solution precipitated ferric hydroxide, while the clear filtrate gave usual tests for benzamidoxime. The presence of any oxidation product of the reagent could not, however, be detected in the filtrate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzamidoxime was prepared by refluxing benzonitrile (1 mol.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 mol.) and sodium hydroxide (1 mol.) in alcoholic solution for 18 hours. The alcohol was then distilled off and the oily residue was dissolved in hot water, decolorised with activated charcoal, and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and cooled in an ice-bath till the separated oil crystallised out. This was filtered off, washed with ice-cold water, and purified by dissolving in benzene and then precipitating with petroleum ether. The product was recrystallised repeatedly from water, followed by a treatment with benzene and petroleum ether till it gave a definite m. p. 78-79° (Krüg, *loc. cit.*). [Found: N, 20.39. Calc. for C₆H₅.C(NH₂):NOH; N, 20.59 per cent].

Copper Benzamidoxime.—A solution of copper^{II} chloride was treated with that of an excess of benzamidoxime and sodium acetate. The green coloured precipitate was filtered off, washed thoroughly with water and dried in air.

The substance is insoluble in water, soluble in acetic acid and mineral acids, as also in ammonia solution. The bluish green solution first formed in ammonia becomes colorless with an excess of the latter on account of reduction of cupric to cuprous state. On treatment with caustic alkalis the copper compound ultimately gives rise to cuprous oxide. The substance decomposes readily on heating and is paramagnetic. $\chi_g = 2.723 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 614.7 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.23$. [Found: Cu, 29.30; N, 12.95. C₆H₅.C(NH₂):NO.Cu(OH) requires Cu, 29.47; N, 12.99 per cent].

Palladium Benzamidoxime.—Palladium^{II} chloride, dissolved in an excess of sodium chloride solution, was treated with an aqueous solution of the requisite quantity of the amidoxime, and the mixture was allowed to stand for some time. The yellowish orange precipitate of the palladium complex was filtered off, washed first with 0.3% hydrochloric acid and then with water, and finally dried over calcium chloride for several days.

The substance is insoluble in water, soluble in acids and in ammonia, but not in caustic alkalis. It is diamagnetic. $\chi_g = -0.5018 \times 10^{-6}$. $\chi_M = -198.1 \times 10^{-6}$. [Found:

Pd, 26.94; N, 14.05. Pd[ON:(H₂N) C₆H₅]₂.H₂O requires Pd, 27.03; N, 14.19 per cent).

Cobalt Benzamidoxime.—An aqueous solution of [Co(C₆H₅N)₄ Cl₂].Cl, 6H₂O (1 mol.) was treated with that of benzamidoxime (3 mol.) in the cold. The green solution turned red. This was then carefully neutralised with sodium hydroxide when a blue precipitate separated out. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with cold water and dried over sulphuric acid *in vacuo*. The dried product is brownish black in colour.

The substance is insoluble in water but soluble in acids. When freshly precipitated it dissolves in alkalis to form a very deep blue solution. The substance is paramagnetic. $\chi_g = 17.96 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 4130 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_s = 3.18$. [Found: Co, 25.68; N, 12.55. C₆H₅.C(NH₂):NO Co(OH)₂ requires Co, 25.77; N, 12.23 per cent].

Red Nickel Compound.—An aqueous solution of nickel chloride (1 mol.) was treated with that of benzamidoxime (3 mol.) and to the mixture ammonia was gradually added till a clear solution was obtained. This was slightly warmed on the water-bath and then filtered. The clear blue filtrate was allowed to stand for several days in a loosely covered vessel, from which red shining crystals gradually separated. These were filtered off, washed first with ice-cold ammoniacal water, then with cold water and finally dried in air.

The substance is slightly soluble in cold water but decomposed by hot water. The aqueous solution reacts faintly alkaline. It is highly soluble in alcohol, acetone, and ether to form a ruby-red solution. It dissolves in caustic alkalis and in ammonia to form a deep blue solution. It is decomposed by acids and liberates iodine from acidified potassium iodide. When gently heated it suffers decomposition with the formation of a black residue. When treated with dilute caustic alkali solution the substance liberates ammonia even in the cold. The substance is diamagnetic. $\chi_g = -0.1394 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = -68.96 \times 10^{-6}$. [Found: Ni, 11.71; N, 22.41. {Ni [C₆H₅.C (:NO) N:N (HON:) C. C₆H₅] [C₆H₅.C (NH₂):NO] (NH₂)₂} requires Ni, 11.57; N, 22.64 per cent].

Blue Nickel Compound (potassium salt).—When the red nickel complex was treated with caustic potash in alcohol, a deep blue solution was obtained. A blue solid was precipitated from it by the addition of absolute ether. The product was dissolved in acetone and reprecipitated with ether. This was dried over calcium chloride and caustic potash.

The substance is highly soluble in water, alcohol and acetone. It is decomposed by acids and even by carbon dioxide. Its aqueous solution hydrolyses and reacts strongly alkaline. The substance is diamagnetic. $\chi_g = -0.3242 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = -134.8 \times 10^{-6}$. [Found: Ni, 14.32; K, 9.63; N, 17.14. {Ni [C₆H₅.C (NH₂):NO] [C₆H₅.C (NO):NO] (OH) (NH₂)} K requires Ni, 14.12; K, 9.39; N, 16.85 per cent].

The magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy's method.

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